
The Influence of Lobbying and Electoral Financing in the Pharmaceutical Sector

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Note: This science communication piece was prepared on the basis of the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector*” [1], authored by the same researcher, and derives from the doctoral dissertation entitled “*The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy: Growth, Influence, Deviations, and Marketing*” [2].

The global rise of the pharmaceutical industry

Over the past century, since the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928, the pharmaceutical sector has undergone profound productive, organizational, and political transformations [2]. Companies that were initially small, often family-run, and limited to local markets [3] gradually gave way to large multinational corporations valued at hundreds of billions of dollars [4], with a global presence [5] and increasing influence over scientific agendas, clinical practices, and regulatory arenas [1, 2].

This process of expansion resulted from the convergence of scientific and technological advances – such as the development of new medicines [6, 7, 8] – and broader socioeconomic transformations, including accelerated urbanization, industrial growth, mass production, rising per capita income, expanded access to health systems, and improvements in educational attainment [9, 10]. Taken together, these dynamics intensified demand for pharmaceuticals and consolidated their centrality as a recurring response to health problems across diverse social contexts [2].

Beyond these widely recognized determinants, however, critical scholarship has drawn attention to the adoption of controversial practices of corporate influence by the pharmaceutical sector. These practices are synthesized in the expression “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the pharmaceutical sector*” [1] and organized into eight major analytical categories: (i) lobbying and electoral financing; (ii) influence over regulatory and oversight bodies; (iii) influence on patient organizations; (iv) influence on the development of clinical guidelines; (v) manipulation, selective promotion, and concealment of drug research and clinical trials; (vi) ghostwriting; (vii) strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering);

and (viii) the financing and provision of benefits to prescribers and institutions, including psychosocial mechanisms and formative dimensions.

Rather than constituting isolated or sporadic conduct, these mechanisms operate in a structural and institutionalized manner, generating cumulative effects on public policies, regulatory processes, the production and circulation of scientific evidence, clinical guidelines, and therapeutic decision-making.

Within this broader framework, the present scientific presentation focuses exclusively on the first of these categories. It examines, in a concise and didactic manner, how lobbying practices and electoral financing have influenced the pharmaceutical sector and shaped relations among corporations, the state, and decision-making processes in the field of health.

Where politics meets health

Although legislators do not act directly in the provision of patient care, they play a central role in shaping health systems. Their decisions influence the financing, provision, and regulation of medical services, as well as the conduct of scientific research and the approval, pricing, and commercialization of medicines and medical devices. In this context, the political system becomes a strategic arena of contestation for economic sectors endowed with substantial financial power – among them, the pharmaceutical industry.

In most countries, lawmakers and public authorities are exposed to the activities of lobbyists: professionals specialized in influencing political decisions in favor of specific interests. These agents are hired by companies, associations, and other organizations to represent their objectives before public authorities, operating through direct negotiation with legislators as well as through coordinated communication campaigns aimed at shaping public opinion or mobilizing financial support for candidates aligned with their agendas. Although lobbying is permitted – or at least tolerated – in many national contexts, it has been the object of persistent criticism due to the disproportionate influence certain groups may exert over decision-making processes, particularly when supported by large volumes of financial resources.

Billions in lobbying and privileged access

The most emblematic illustration of this dynamic in the pharmaceutical sector is found in the United States, where lobbying activity is formally regulated and, unlike in most countries, public databases allow for systematic analysis. U.S. legislation authorizes citizens and organizations to hire professionals to debate and influence public policies; in practice, however, this system has given rise to a dense web of political relationships sustained by multibillion-dollar investments, raising profound concerns regarding democratic balance and regulatory capture.

An analysis of data from the OpenSecrets repository shows that the so-called “pharmaceutical and health products industry” has substantially expanded its lobbying expenditures. Over the longest period for which data are available, sectoral spending increased by 436%, rising from US\$69.6 million in 1998 to US\$373.7 million in 2022 (Figure 1). In total, US\$5.45 billion were invested during this interval, positioning the sector as the

Figure 1. Annual lobbying expenditures of the pharmaceutical and health products industry in the United States (1998-2022, US\$). Source: OpenSecrets (2023).

largest lobbying spender among all economic segments in the country, with expenditures approximately 60% higher than those of the second-ranked sector, the insurance industry.

This expansion in financial investment was accompanied by a marked increase in the number of registered lobbyists representing the sector, which rose from 747 professionals in 1998 to 1,840 in 2022 [11]. Of these individuals, 64.35% are former government employees, evidencing the revolving-door phenomenon. This process is characterized by the migration of former regulators, public servants, and even members of Congress into lobbying positions within private corporations – often in policy areas they previously oversaw or regulated.

Electoral financing and legislative influence

In addition to direct lobbying, individuals and corporate organizations frequently resort to electoral campaign financing as a strategy of political influence. To strengthen institutional ties and expand their capacity for pressure, large corporations commonly distribute resources across multiple candidates and political parties. While lobbying and electoral contributions pursue similar objectives and raise comparable concerns regarding democratic quality, they constitute distinct instruments, each subject to specific regulations and budgetary classifications within the U.S. political system.

Available data indicate that the pharmaceutical and health products industry made electoral contributions totaling US\$292.5 million to the United States Congress over the past three decades (Figure 2). During this period, contributions increased approximately seventeenfold, rising from US\$3.1 million in the 1990 electoral cycle to US\$52 million in 2020. Although information related to the federal executive branch is more limited, it is estimated that approximately US\$51 million were allocated to candidates in the four most recent presidential elections.

Figure 2. Electoral contributions of the pharmaceutical and health products industry to candidates for the United States Congress and Presidency, by electoral cycle (1990-2020, US\$). Source: OpenSecrets (2023).

Similar patterns were identified by Wouters (2020) [12], who documented even higher levels of contributions to state-level candidates and committees, totaling US\$877 million between 1999 and 2018. According to the author, these disbursements intensified in years marked by major debates and referendums on drug pricing and regulation. In the 2020 electoral cycle alone, at least 2,467 state legislators – more than one third of all such officials in the United States – received campaign financing from the pharmaceutical industry [13].

The allocation of these resources is not random. Members of Congress serving on committees of strategic relevance to the sector’s interests tend to receive larger volumes of donations [14], while legislators who advocate for policies aimed at reducing drug prices frequently become targets of smear campaigns. These campaigns range from nationally broadcast advertising to direct mailings containing fabricated or misleading content sent to voters [15].

When influence costs lives

The persistence of these practices over time suggests that high levels of investment in lobbying and electoral financing have proven economically effective. Consolidated data show that the pharmaceutical industry generated more than half a trillion dollars in revenue from drug sales in the United States in 2021 alone (Figure 3). Between 2002 and 2021, pharmaceutical sales in the country increased by 194.4%, resulting in cumulative revenue of US\$7.12 trillion.

The consequences of this influence become particularly evident when examined in the context of one of the most severe public health crises in recent U.S. history: the opioid epidemic, which claimed the lives of more than one million people between 1999 and 2024 [16] [17] [18]. An investigation conducted by The Washington Post, led by Higham and Bernstein (2017), documented how pharmaceutical industry lobbying contributed to weakening the enforcement capacity of the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) in monitoring and regulating the opioid trade [19].

Members of Congress who received campaign financing from political action committees linked to the pharmaceutical sector played a central role in advancing the Ensuring Patient Access and Effective Drug Enforcement Act. In practice, this legislation curtailed the DEA's enforcement authority and favored drug distribution companies that supplied potent and highly addictive opioids to healthcare professionals involved in illicit schemes.

The investigation further revealed that, between 2000 and 2017, at least 56 officials from the DEA and the U.S. Department of Justice transitioned into positions within the pharmaceutical industry. Among them was a former deputy chief counsel of the DEA, who played a pivotal role in drafting the legislation responsible for diminishing the enforcement power of his former agency [19].

Five years later, in 2022, Joe Rannazzisi, then head of the DEA's pharmaceutical enforcement division, reaffirmed the persistence of these dynamics. Upon leaving his position, he stated that he and his team had faced intense and sustained pressure from highly organized campaigns involving lobbyists, legislators, executives, and attorneys financed by the pharmaceutical industry, underscoring the depth and resilience of these power networks [20].

Conclusion – structural influence and democratic challenges

Taken together, the evidence examined indicates that lobbying and electoral financing constitute one of the principal structural axes of political influence exercised by the pharmaceutical industry. Far from being confined to episodic practices or individual relationships, these mechanisms operate in an institutionalized manner, sustained by large financial volumes, privileged access to decision-makers, and the recurrent circulation of actors between the public and private sectors. The outcome is the consolidation of a normative

Figure 3. Annual revenue from pharmaceutical sales in the United States (2002-2021, US\$). Source: Statista (2023).

and regulatory environment in which highly concentrated economic interests exert disproportionate influence over policies that directly affect collective health. Understanding these dynamics is therefore essential not only for enriching public debate, but also for informing institutional responses aimed at confronting political capture and strengthening transparency, integrity, and the collective interest within the pharmaceutical sector.

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